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EXPANSION AND DEVELOPMENT OF ROAD NETWORKS (FOR EXAMPLE, THE INTERSECTION OF M. ULUGBEK AND GAGARIN STREETS)

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Annotation: Before proceeding to the development of measures for the improvement and improvement of the trunk network of the Central zone of Samarkand, the trunk network of the center throughout the city, it is necessary to determine the necessary capabilities of the street and road network of the Central Zone. If measures are not taken to divert transit traffic from the center, the street and road network of the Central Zone will not cope with the traffic load. Improving the conditions of circulation of traffic flows in the central zone is associated with the diversion of transit traffic from it. The above practical recommendations can be achieved by implementing them for the purpose of design and practical application on other densely populated, busy streets of our republic. The proposed project - a "three-storey overpass" will prevent congestion at the intersection of Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin Streets, which is one of the main and busiest streets of the city of Samarkand.

Keywords: streets, overpasses, rush hour, intersection, road network,

The plan of the proposed road to the existing

Introduction. The master plan of the green master plan of the Bogishamol intersection, areas, pedestrian walkways, and existing where Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets meet, buildings located around the Bogishamol has been designed intersection where Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets meet has been designed.

Figure 1. Horizontal view of the proposed object

On the basis of the above data, a project 3- Bogishamol, at the junction of Mirzo Ulugbek dimensional (3D) junction was developed, and Gagarin streets. which is being proposed at the intersection of

Through this proposed project, traffic is taken from the traffic jam at the junction of Bogishamol, at the junction of Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets, which is part of one of the main and traffic streets of Samarkand City,

in which traffic lights are expected to light a 3-time green light in some cases. Taking into account the width of the traffic lane and the large number of car traffic, the four directions of the intersection are embodied by the lighting of the green light of a separate traffic light for traffic traffic, at the junction of Bogishamol with the current Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets. This is due to the fact that we can observe that the expectation of traffic at the junction of Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets at the junction of Bogishamol increases by 3 times in relation to intersections with equal concurrent traffic in opposite movements at the intersection.

The difference between the proposed bridge project from most other bridge projects at the junction of Bogishamol with the junction of Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets is as follows:

- 1) designed as a floor bridge to move in all directions, including for turning;
- 2) despite the fact that the object is a one-story bridge, there is no svetefor in it, traffic is continuous. That is, the proposal project is designed in such a way that the movement of transports to all sides is provided even without a traffic light;
- 3) there is no need to demolish existing built-up buildings and push them into the ditch, the

traffic is planned to be continuous if you pay attention to this designed structure. In its current state, especially at the time of chaspik, traffic has become known in research work, existing gabarite of the road was used to the maximum;

4) the area consumption for the construction of a one-story bridge for four-way traffic was designed to be minimal. This does not mean that the bridge for traffic will be defective, narrow, thin. On the contrary, you can pay attention to the fact that it is designed very comfortable and cozy;

5) the proposed project can be designed not only in the Samarkand region, but also in the dense, congested streets of the Republic.

Figure 2. Outline of the proposed object.

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In order to increase the culture of services to the population, to create favorable conditions, a broad emphasis is placed on the Prevention of traffic jams in large urban centers, densely populated areas and cities of the Republic.

The expansion and development of road networks greatly accelerates the pace of industrial, construction and especially urban development

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It can be seen that if the speed in the existing chorrachas reaches a transition period of 4.5-7.5 minutes when green-lit 2.3.4 times, then there is a period of continuation of the path or path through a small ring road, or 1 minute with other reasons that extend 20 seconds. This

not only prevents congestion, but also contributes a lot to the Prevention of urban air pollution by reducing exhaust gases from motor vehicles. By applying a small ring road in the chorrachas, where the motor vehicle traffic has accelerated, we will have achieved efficiency from the time of harvest to the ecological niche. Because it does not allow traffic jams and reduces the impact of exhaust gases that are releasing into the ecology. It is known that a motor vehicle driven out of place releases 2.1% more exhaust gas than an exhaust gas coming out of a stationary vehicle.

Conclusion.

The first importance of our government is aimed at ensuring the rapid implementation of projects for the construction and reconstruction of highways that are part of urban highways, the creation of a single national road transport system that reliably connects all regions of our country.

Taking into account this, special attention is paid to further improving the quality of the road traffic system in our Republic, their

reconstruction and modernization in accordance with the national and international standards adopted by the highway network, the construction of new and convenient urban streets. Every year, a large amount of investment from the state budget is being directed for the development of the transport system.

In conclusion, the project of the proposed bridge at the junction of Mirzo Ulugbek and Gagarin streets in order to avoid high-rise roads in areas with unfavorable terrain in the management of traffic on urban streets, to avoid situations of fragility in traffic jams and intersections, despite the fact that it is a single-storey bridge, traffic traffic is continuous; There is no need to demolish existing built-up buildings and push them into the ditch, the existing gabarite of the road was used to the maximum extent; the proposed project and the work done can be achieved by bringing to life the above practical recommendations for the purpose of designing and putting them into practice not only in the Samarkand region, but also in

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